

Comon Fixed Point Theorems for Four Self Mapping in D–Metric Spaces¹

Dr. Manoj Kumar Tiwari

Guest Lecturer, Department of Mathematics, Govt. Mata Shabari Naveen Girls P.G. College,
Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh, India

Abstract

In this paper we used the concept of compatible mappings of type (P) in D-metric space. Our result generalize the result of Fisher and Parsai V. and Singh B.

Keywords

Common Fixed Point, D–Metric Space, Compatible Maps, Compatible Maps of Type(P).

Introduction

Dhage introduced a new structure of a generalized metric space which was an extension of the ordinary metric space.in 1992, defined as follows,

Let \mathbb{R} denoted the real line and X denoted a nonempty set. Let $D : X \times X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function satisfying properties:

(D₁) $D(x, y, z) \geq 0$ for all $x, y, z \in X$, equality holds if and only if $x = y = z$.

(D₂) $D(x, y, z) = D(x, z, y) = \dots \dots \dots \forall x, y, z \in X$,

(D₃) $D(x, y, z) \leq D(x, y, u) + D(x, u, z) + D(u, y, z) \forall x, y, z, u \in X$,

The function D is called a D-metric for the space X and (X, D) denotes a D-metric space. Generally the usual ordinary metric is called the distance function. D-metric is called diameter function of the points of X .

In the last four decades, a number of authors have studied the aspects of fixed point theory in the setting of D-metric spaces.. Khan, Murthy-Chang-Cho-Sharma and Naidu-Prasad introduced the concepts of weakly commuting pairs of self mappings, compatible pairs of self mapping of type (A) in a D-metric space and notion of weak continuity of a D-metric, respectively, and they have proved several common fixed point theorems by using the weakly commuting pairs of self-mappings, compatible pairs of self- mappings of type (A) in a D-metric space and the weak continuity of a D-metric.

In this research paper, I have used the concept of compatible mappings of type (P) and compare these mappings with compatible mappings and compatible mappings of type (A) in D-metric spaces. In the

¹Address Author Correspondence to Dr. Manoj Kumar Tiwari at mt.maths@gmail.com

Accepted: 05 January 2024 / Published online: 29 January 2024

© The Author(s), 2024. Paper ID, 300457.

sequel, we drive some relations between these mappings. Also, we prove a coincidence point a common fixed point theorem for compatible mappings of type (P) in D-metric spaces.

Definitions [1]: A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a D-metric space (X, D) is said to be convergent to a point $x \in X$, denoted by $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(x_n, x, z) = 0$ for all $z \in X$. The point x is said to be limit of sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X .

Definition [2]: A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a D-metric space (X, D) is called a Cauchy sequence if $D(x_m, x_n, z) \rightarrow 0$ as $n, m \rightarrow \infty$ for all $z \in X$.

Definition [3]: A D-metric space in which every Cauchy sequence is convergent is called complete.

Remark [1]: In a D-metric space (X, D) a convergent sequence need not be a Cauchy sequence, but every convergent sequence is a Cauchy sequence when the D-metric D is continuous on X .

Definition [4]: Let S and T be mappings from a D-metric space (X, D) into itself. The mappings S and T are said to be compatible if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(STx_n, TSx_n, z) = 0$ for all $z \in X$, whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n = t$ for some $t \in X$.

Definition [5]: Let S and T be mappings from a D-metric space (X, D) into itself. The mappings S and T are said to be compatible of type (A) if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(STx_n, TTx_n, z) = 0$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(STx_n, SSx_n, z) = 0$ for all $z \in X$, whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n = t$ for some $t \in X$.

Definition [6]: Let S and T be mappings from a D-metric space (X, D) into itself. The mappings S and T are said to be compatible of type (P) if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(SSx_n, TTx_n, z) = 0$ for all $z \in X$, whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n = t$ for some $t \in X$.

The following propositions show that Definition [3.5] & [3.6] are equivalent under some conditions:

Proposition [1]: Let S and T be compatible mappings of type(P) from a D-metric space (X, D) into itself. If $St = Tt$ for some t in X , Then $STt = SSt = TTt = TSt$.

Proof : Suppose that $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X defined by $x_n = t$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ and $St = Tt$. Then we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Sx_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Tx_n = St$. Since S and T are compatible mappings of type (P), we have $D(SSt, TTt, z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} D(SSx_n, TTx_n, z) = 0$.

Hence we have $SSt = TTt$. Therefore, $STt = SSt = TTt = TSt$.

Let R^+ denote the set of all non-negative real numbers and F be the family of mappings $\phi : (R^+)^5 \rightarrow R^+$ such that each ϕ is upper-semi-continuous, non-decreasing in each coordinate variable, and for any $t > 0$, $\gamma(t) = \phi(t, t, a_1t, a_2t, t) < t$, where $\gamma : R^+ \rightarrow R^+$ is a mapping with $\gamma(0) = 0$ and $a_1 + a_2 = 3$.

We have prove the following theorems:

Theorem [1.1]: Let A, B, S and T be mappings from a complete D-metric space (X, D) into itself, satisfying the following conditions:

- [1.1] $A(X) \subset T(X)$ and $B(X) \subset S(X)$,
 [1.2] $S(X) \cap T(X)$ is a complete subspace of X .
 [1.3] $[1+p\{D(Ax, Sx, z) + D(By, Ty, z)\}] D(Ax, By, z)$

$$\leq p[D^2(Ax, Sx, z) + D^2(By, Ty, z)] + \phi(D(Sx, Ty, z), D(Ax, Sx, z), D(By, Ty, z), (Ax, Ty, z), D(By, Sx, z))$$

for all $x, y, z \in X$, where $\phi \in F$. Then the pairs A, S and B, T have a coincidence point in X .

For our theorems, we need the following LEMMAS:

Lemma [1]: For every $t > 0$, $\gamma(t) < t$ if and only if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \gamma^n(t) = 0$, where γ^n denotes the n -times composition of γ .

Lemma [2]: Let A, B, S and T be mappings from a complete D -metric space (X, D) into itself, satisfying the conditions [3.1.1], [3.4.3]. Then we have the following :

- a. For every $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $D(y_n, y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}) = 0$,
- b. For every $i, j, k \in \mathbb{N}_0$, $D(y_i, y_j, y_k) = 0$, where $\{y_n\}$ is the sequence in X defined by [1.4].

Proof of The Lemma: (a) By(3.1.1) since $A(X) \subset T(X)$, for any arbitrary point $x_0 \in X$, there exists a point $x_1 \in X$ such that $Ax_0 = Tx_1$. Since $B(X) \subset S(X)$, for any arbitrary point $x_1 \in X$, there exists a point $x_2 \in X$ such that $Bx_1 = Sx_2$ and so on. Inductively, we can define a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in X such that

$$[1.4] \quad y_{2n} = Tx_{2n+1} = Ax_{2n} \text{ and } y_{2n+1} = Sx_{2n+2} = Bx_{2n+1} \text{ for } n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

In [1.3], taking $x = x_{2n+2}$, $y = x_{2n+1}$, $z = x_{2n}$ we have,

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, y_{2n}) + D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, y_{2n})\}] D(Ax_{2n+2}, Bx_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \\ \leq p[D^2(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, y_{2n}) + D^2(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, y_{2n})] \\ + \phi(D(Sx_{2n+2}, Tx_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), D(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, y_{2n}), \\ D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), D(Ax_{2n+2}, Tx_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), D(Bx_{2n+1}, Sx_{2n+2}, y_{2n})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) + D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n})\}] D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \\ \leq p[D^2(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) + D^2(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n})] \\ + \phi(D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}), D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}), \\ D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n}, y_{2n}), D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) + 0\}] D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) \\ \leq p[D^2(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) + 0] + \phi(0, D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), 0, 0, 0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) &\leq \phi(0, D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}), 0, 0, 0) \\ &< D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}). \end{aligned}$$

which is a contradiction. Thus we have $D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}) = 0$,

similarly, we have $D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, y_{2n-1}) = 0$.

Hence, for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, we have [1.4] $D(y_{n+2}, y_{n+1}, y_n) = 0$.

(b) For all $z \in X$, let $d_n(z) = D(y_n, y_{n+1}, z)$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.

By (a), we have

$$D(y_n, y_{n+2}, z) \leq D(y_n, y_{n+2}, y_{n+1}) + D(y_n, y_{n+1}, z) + D(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}, z)$$

$$D(y_n, y_{n+2}, z) \leq D(y_n, y_{n+1}, z) + D(y_{n+1}, y_{n+2}, z)$$

$$D(y_n, y_{n+2}, z) \leq d_n(z) + d_{n+1}(z)$$

Taking $x = x_{2n+2}$ and $y = x_{2n+1}$ in [3.1.3], we have

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, z) + D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z)\}] D(Ax_{2n+2}, Bx_{2n+1}, z) \\ \leq p[D^2(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, z) + D^2(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z)] + \phi(D(Sx_{2n+2}, Tx_{2n+1}, z), \\ D(Ax_{2n+2}, Sx_{2n+2}, z), D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z), D(Ax_{2n+2}, Tx_{2n+1}, z), \\ D(Bx_{2n+1}, Sx_{2n+2}, z)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, z) + D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z)\}] D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, z) \\ \leq p[D^2(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, z) + D^2(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z)] + \phi(D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n+1}, z), \\ D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, z)) \end{aligned}$$

$$D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+2}, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}, z))$$

$$[1.5] [1+p\{d_{2n+1}(z) + d_{2n}(z)\}] d_{2n+1}(z)$$

$$\leq p[D^{2n+1}(z) + D^{2n}(z)] + \phi(d_{2n}(z), d_{2n+1}(z), d_{2n}(z), \{d_{2n}(z) + d_{2n+1}(z)\}, 0)$$

Now, we shall show that $\{d_n(z)\}$ is a non increasing sequence in \mathbb{R}^+ . In fact, let $d_{n+1}(z) > d_n(z)$ for some n .

By [1.5] we have, $d_{2n+1}(z) < d_{2n+1}(z)$, which is a contradiction in \mathbb{R}^+ .

Now, we claim that $d_n(y_m) = 0$ for all non negative integers m, n .

Case 1. $n \geq m$. Then we have $0 = d_m(y_m) \geq d_n(y_m)$.

Case 2. $n < m$. By (M_4), we have

$$d_n(y_m) \leq d_n(y_{m-1}) + d_{m-1}(y_n) \leq d_n(y_{m-1}) + d_n(y_n) = d_n(y_{m-1})$$

By using the above inequality repeatedly, we have

$$d_n(y_m) \leq d_n(y_{m-1}) \leq d_n(y_{m-2}) \leq \dots \leq d_n(y_n) = 0,$$

which completes the proof of our claim.

Finally, let i, j , and k be arbitrary non-negative integers. We may assume that $i < j$. By (M_4), we have

$$D(y_i, y_j, y_k) \leq d_i(y_j) + d_i(y_k) + D(y_{i+1}, y_j, y_k) = D(y_{i+1}, y_j, y_k).$$

Therefore, by repetition of the above inequality, we have

$$D(y_i, y_j, y_k) \leq D(y_{i+1}, y_j, y_k) \leq \dots \leq D(y_i, y_j, y_k) = 0.$$

This completes the proof.

Lemma [3]: Let A, B, S and T be mappings from a D -metric space (X, D) into itself satisfying the following conditions [1.1] and [1.3]. Then the sequence $\{y_n\}$ defined by [1.4] is a Cauchy sequence in X .

Proof of The Lemma : In the proof of LEMMA [2], since $d_n(z)$ is a non increasing sequence in \mathbb{R}^+ , by [1.3], we have ,

$$\begin{aligned} [1+p\{D(Ax_2, Sx_2, z) + D(Bx_1, Tx_1, z)\}] D(Ax_2, Bx_1, z) \\ \leq p[d^2(Ax_2, Sx_2, z) + d^2(Bx_1, Tx_1, z)] + \phi(D(Sx_2, Tx_1, z), D(Ax_2, Sx_2, z), D(Bx_1, Tx_1, z), \\ D(Ax_2, Tx_1, z), D(Bx_1, Sx_2, z)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [1+p\{D(y_2, y_1, z) + D(y_1, y_0, z)\}] D(y_2, y_1, z) \\
 & \leq p[d^2(y_2, y_1, z) + d^2(y_1, y_0, z)] + \phi(D(y_1, y_0, z), D(y_2, y_1, z), D(y_1, y_0, z), \\
 & D(y_2, y_0, z), D(y_1, y_1, z))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$[1+p\{d_1(z) + d_0(z)\}] d_1(z) \leq p[d^2_1(z) + d^2_0(z)] + \phi(d_0(z), d_1(z), d_0(z), \{d_0(z)+d_1(z)\}, 0)$$

$$d_1(z) \leq \phi(d_0(z), d_0(z), d_0(z), \{d_0(z)+d_0(z)\}, 0)$$

$$d_1(z) \leq \gamma(d_0(z))$$

$$\text{and } d_2(z) \leq \gamma(d_1(z)) \leq \gamma(\gamma(d_0(z))) = \gamma^2(d_0(z)).$$

In general, we have $d_n(z) \leq \gamma^n(d_0(z))$.

Thus, if $d_0(z) > 0$, by LEMMA [3.1] $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_n(z) = 0$. If $d_0(z) = 0$, we have clearly $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_n(z) = 0$ since $d_n(z) = 0$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$

Now, we shall prove that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_n(z) = 0$, it is sufficient to show that a subsequence $\{y_{2n}\}$ of $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . Suppose that the sequence $\{y_{2n}\}$ is not a Cauchy sequence in X . Then there exist a point $z \in X$, an $\varepsilon > 0$ and strictly increasing sequences $\{m(k)\}, \{n(k)\}$ of positive integers such that $k \leq n(k) < m(k)$,

$$[1.6] \quad (y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) \geq \varepsilon \text{ and } D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) < \varepsilon$$

for all $k = 1, 2, \dots$. By LEMMA[3.2] and (M_4) , we have

$$D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) - D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k-2)}, z) \leq D(y_{2m(k-2)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) \leq d_{2m(k-2)}(z) + d_{2m(k-1)}(z)$$

Since $\{D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) - \varepsilon\}$ and $\{\varepsilon - D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k-2)}, z)\}$ are sequences in \mathbb{R}^+ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_n(z) = 0$, we have

$$[1.7] \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k)}, z) = \varepsilon \text{ and } \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k-2)}, z) = \varepsilon$$

Note that, by (M_4) , we have

$$[1.8] \quad |D(x, y, a) - D(x, y, b)| \leq D(a, b, x) + D(a, b, y)$$

for all $x, y, a, b \in X$. Taking $x = y_{2n(k)}, y = a, a = y_{2m(k-1)}$ and $b = y_{2m(k)}$ in [1.8] and using lemma [2] and [1.7], we have

$$[1.9] \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} D(y_{2n(k)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z) = \varepsilon.$$

Once again, by using lemma [2], [1.7] and [1.8], we have

$$[1.10] \quad \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} D(y_{2n(k)+1}, y_{2m(k)}, z) = \varepsilon \text{ and } \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} D(y_{2n(k-1)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z) = \varepsilon.$$

Thus, by [1.3], we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
 [1.11] \quad & [1+p\{D(Ax_{2m(k)}, Sx_{2m(k)}, z) + D(Bx_{2n(k+1)}, Tx_{2n(k+1)}, z)\}] D(Ax_{2m(k)}, Bx_{2n(k+1)}, z) \\
 & \leq p[d^2(Ax_{2m(k)}, Sx_{2m(k)}, z) + d^2(Bx_{2n(k+1)}, Tx_{2n(k+1)}, z)] \\
 & \quad + \phi(D(Sx_{2m(k)}, Tx_{2n(k+1)}, z), D(Ax_{2m(k)}, Sx_{2m(k)}, z), \\
 & \quad D(Bx_{2n(k+1)}, Tx_{2n(k+1)}, z), \\
 & \quad D(Ax_{2m(k)}, Tx_{2n(k+1)}, z), D(Bx_{2n(k+1)}, Sx_{2m(k)}, z))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & [1+p\{D(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z) + D(y_{2n(k+1)}, y_{2n(k)}, z)\}] D(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k+1)}, z) \\
 & \leq p[d^2(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z) + d^2(y_{2n(k+1)}, y_{2n(k)}, z)] + \phi(D(y_{2m(k-1)}, y_{2n(k)}, z), \\
 & D(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z), D(y_{2n(k+1)}, y_{2n(k)}, z), D(y_{2m(k)}, y_{2n(k)}, z), \\
 & D(y_{2n(k+1)}, y_{2m(k-1)}, z))
 \end{aligned}$$

As $k \rightarrow \infty$ in [1.11] and noting that d is continuous, we have

$$\varepsilon \leq \phi(\varepsilon, 0, 0, \varepsilon, \varepsilon) < \gamma(\varepsilon) < \varepsilon$$

which is a contradiction. Therefore, $\{y_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X and so the sequence $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in X . This completes the proof.

Proof of The Theorem : By lemma[3], the sequence $\{y_n\}$ defined by [1.2] is a Cauchy sequence in $S(X) \cap T(X)$. Since $S(X) \cap T(X)$ is a complete subspace of X , $\{y_n\}$ converges to a point w in $S(X) \cap T(X)$. On the other hand, since the subsequences $\{y_{2n}\}$ and $\{y_{2n+1}\}$ of $\{y_n\}$ are also Cauchy sequences in $S(X) \cap T(X)$, they also converge to the same limit w . Hence there exist two points u, v in X such that $Su = w$ and $Tv = w$, respectively.

By [1.3], we have

$$\begin{aligned} & [1+p\{D(Au, Su, z) + D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z)\}] D(Au, Bx_{2n+1}, z) \\ & \leq p[d^2(Au, Su, z) + d^2(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z)] + \phi(D(Su, Tx_{2n+1}, z), \\ & \quad D(Au, Su, z), D(Bx_{2n+1}, Tx_{2n+1}, z), D(Au, Tx_{2n+1}, z), D(Bx_{2n+1}, Su, z)) \\ & [1+p\{D(Au, Su, z) + D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z)\}] D(Au, y_{2n+1}, z) \\ & \leq p[d^2(Au, Su, z) + d^2(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z)] + \phi(D(Su, y_{2n}, z), D(Au, Su, z), \\ & \quad D(y_{2n+1}, y_{2n}, z), D(Au, y_{2n}, z), D(y_{2n+1}, Su, z)) \end{aligned}$$

Since $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d_n(z) = 0$ in the proof of Lemma2, letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & [1+p\{D(Au, w, z) + D(w, w, z)\}] D(Au, w, z) \\ & \leq p[d^2(Au, w, z) + d^2(w, w, z)] + \phi(D(w, w, z), D(Au, w, z), D(w, w, z), \\ & \quad D(Au, w, z), D(w, w, z)) \end{aligned}$$

$D(Au, w, z) \leq \phi(0, D(Au, w, z), 0, D(Au, w, z), 0) < \gamma(D(Au, w, z)) < D(Au, w, z)$ which is contradiction .

Hence $Au = w = Sw$, that is u is a coincidence of A and S .

Similarly, we can show that v is a coincidence point of B and T .

Reference

1. Constantin, A. : Common fixed points of Weakly Commuting Mappings in D-Metric spaces, Math. Japon., 36(3) (1991), 507-514.
2. Constantin, A., (1994): On some fixed point theorems in metric spaces, Univ. u Novom sadu Zb. Rad. prirod. - mat.Fak.Ser.mat. 24,2,9-21.
3. Das B.K. and Gupta S. (1975): An Extension of Banach Contraction Principle Through Retional Expression, Ind. J. Pure Appl. Math 6, 1455-58.
4. Dhage, B. C.,(1999): Some results on common fixed points, Indian J. Pure Appl. Math. 30, 827-837.
5. Dhage, B.C., Arya, S., & Ume, J. S.,(2003): A general lemma for fixed point theorems involving more than two maps in D – metric spaces with applications, Int. J. Math. Sci. No. 11, 661 – 672.
6. Fisher , B. : Mathe Sem, Notes, Kobe Univ., 10, 17 – 26(1982).
7. Fisher, B.,(1975) : Fixed point theorems, : Atli. Della. Naz. De. Linces, LIX, Fase 5.

8. Fisher, B.,(1975) : A fixed point theorem : Math. Mag , 48, 223-225.
9. Fisher, B.,(1977): Common fixed points and constant mapping on metric space. Math. Sem. Notes, : Koge. Univ. 5, 319.
10. Fisher,B.,(1982): Mathe Sem, Notes, Kobe Univ.,10,17– 26.
11. Fisher,B.,(1983):Common fixed points of four mappings, Bull. Inst. Math. Acad. Sinica 11, 103-113.
12. Gähler S. (1963/64): D-Metric Raume Und Topologische Struktur, Math. Nachr. 26, 115-148.
13. Gahler, S.: Zur geometric D-metrische Raume, Rev. Roum. De Math. Pures et Appl., 11(1968), 665-667.
14. Imdad, M., Khan, M.S and Khan, M. D. : A common fixed point theorem in D-metric spaces, Math. Japon., 36(5)(1991), 907-914.
15. Iseki, K.,Sharma, P. L. and Sharma, B.K.: Contraction type mappings on D-metric spaces, Math. Japon. 21(1976), 67-70.
16. Iseki, K.: A property of orbitally continuous mappings on D- metric spaces, Math. Sem. Notes, Kobe Univ., 3(1975), 131-132.
17. Khan, M.S.: Convergence of sequence of fixed points in D-metric spaces, Indian J. Pure Appl. Math. (10)(1979), 106D-1067.
18. Khan, M. S.: On fixed point theorems in D-metric spaces. Publ. Inst. Math.(BeograD) (N.S) , 41(1980), 107-112.
19. A. Khan, M. S. and Swaleh: Results Concerning fixed points in D-metric spaces , Mth. Japon. , 29(1984), 519-525.
20. Parsai V. and Singh B.(1991) : Some fixed point theorem in D- metric space, Vikarm math.soc. 33-37.